

Demo: Unifying Softwarised Terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks within O-RAN Architecture

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Abstract—Next generation mobile networks will include Non-Terrestrial networks (NTNs) to complement terrestrial networks (TN) and provide ubiquitous coverage. Achieving a unified operational framework is essential to simplify integration and reduce deployment complexity. This demo presents a unified Central Unit (CU) capable of simultaneously managing Distributed Units (DU) for the TN segment and the NTN segment. The system employs full softwarisation of both domains using cloud-native artefacts, enabling flexible deployment on commercial off-the-shelf hardware and seamless TN–NTN integration without hardware-specific adaptations. The demonstration highlights how the unified CU manages heterogeneous radio access technologies (RATs), and can expose real-time Key Performance Metrics (KPMs) through O-RAN interfaces towards the Near-Real Time Radio Access Network Intelligent Controller (RIC) to provide cross-domain observability. Through live visualization of throughput performance, latency profiles, and resource usage, attendees will observe the operational differences between terrestrial and GEO NTN links under a common control framework. This demo validates a practical and portable architecture for TN–NTN convergence and establishes a foundation for future RIC-driven optimisation and multi-domain intelligence in Beyond 5G/6G networks.

Index Terms—NTN/TN, B5G/6G, GEO, Management and Orchestration, O-RAN, Open5GS, OCUDU

I. INTRODUCTION

Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) will be an integral part of next-generation mobile networks. The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) is working towards their integration with Terrestrial Networks (TNs) to address challenges such as expanding coverage for underserved regions, increasing resilience against disasters, and ensuring connectivity continuity in mobility-extreme scenarios (e.g., maritime, aviation). Other standards development organizations (SDOs), such as the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Alliance, recognize the potential for a unified, open, and intelligent Radio Access Network (RAN), where Centralized Units (CUs), Distributed Units (DUs), and the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) stack support both TN and NTN segments, enabling common control, observability, and automation [1]. While NTN provides coverage and resilience, the real benefits are realized when it is integrated natively with TN RAN rather than operated in isolation. The O-RAN architecture introduces intelligence and

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programmability through the Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC) and the Non-RT RIC/Service Management and Orchestration (SMO), promoting closed-loop control, Key Performance Indicator-driven optimization, and automated, efficient management and orchestration (MANO) procedures to reduce the complexity of integrating multi-component RANs. Thus, intelligent control and unified observability are essential for scalable TN-NTN integrated deployments.

This work advances the unification of TN-NTN RAN, building on previous research in [2]–[4], by decoupling the NTN gNB into independent CU and DU entities using the OCUDU open-source software (formerly the srsRAN project) [5]. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of a shared CU instance shared across domains, providing a common control and data plane between TN and NTN domains. This architectural approach simplifies operations by enabling a central view for analytics and policy distribution. Furthermore, we facilitate integration by connecting both DUs to a Near-RT RIC instance, where we demonstrate how an xApp collects metrics to enable cross-domain observability within a laboratory environment that emulates a realistic transparent geostationary (GEO) scenario. Key performance metrics (KPMs), such as, resource utilization in terms of Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) or throughput are monitored to validate the practical role of Near-RT RIC for TN-NTN convergence. This setup enables future xApps and rApps development to handle scheduling, beam and handover decisions, or resource allocation in delay-challenged satellite links. A distinguishing feature of this demonstration is that all mobile network entities (O-RAN and core) are packaged as cloud-native artefacts and deployed according to MANO principles. Helm charts are included in ETSI NFV Network Service (NS) packages to ensure repeatable and portable deployments on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware. While this work focuses on a transparent GEO scenario combined with a TN segment, this software-based methodology can be extended in future work to regenerative NTN scenarios also considering other orbits, such as Low Earth Orbit (LEO)¹.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows the complete TN-NTN unified setup, which combines CTTC’s CASTLE® platform for Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) research with the xG EXTREME® testbed for Terrestrial

¹Experimentation in regenerative satellite setups involves greater complexity and time-consuming workflows because of the need for dedicated, high-cost infrastructure.

Fig. 1. System Architecture under demonstration showing the unified CU controlling the distributed NTN_DU and TN_DU

Network (TN) scenarios. The NTN segment uses two x64 general-purpose servers running Ubuntu 24.04 LTS and two Ettus USRP X310 SDRs. One of these servers runs our customized 5G NR NTN_UE based on the srsRAN 4G stack. It is a 3GPP Release 17-compliant implementation with proprietary PHY and MAC layer enhancements designed for transparent GEO satellite links. Key modifications include: Doppler shift and large Round Trip Delay (RTD) pre-compensation management, updated Random Access (RACH) procedures and processing of System Information Block 19 (SIB19) for precise Timing Advance (TA) estimation. The second server, named Cluster C, functions as the ground station Point of Presence (PoP) and hosts a single-node Kubernetes (K8s) cluster where NTN_DU NS instances are deployed on demand. The USRP controlled by the NTN_UE is connected directly to the USRP controlled by the gNB with RF cables, and the delay introduced by the satellite is emulated via a software channel emulator that delays the sending and receiving of packets at the NTN_UE side via the use of buffers that vary in length according to the intended GEO satellite altitude.

The TN domain consists of three x64 servers managed by our MANO platform, which runs an instance of ETSI Open Source MANO (OSM). Clusters A and B serve as PoPs, each hosting a single-node K8s cluster where the mobile core, the integrated CU, the TN DU, and the Near-RT RIC NSs are deployed. These entities are deployed based on generated network artefacts (i.e., embedded Helm Charts in OSM packages) using open-source code from Open5GS (mobile core), OCUDU (disaggregated gNB), and the O-RAN Software Community (OSC for the Near-RT RIC), as explained in [6], [7]. The setup is completed on the RAN side with a USRP N210 serving as the radio unit and a Realme 9 smartphone serving as the TN_UE.

The main contribution of this work is the unification of the NTN and TN segments at the CU level after decoupling the execution of the NTN gNB component into independent CU and DU processes. In this process, proper configuration at the NTN DU level was required to address the GEO scenario

(SIB19 processing extension, time advance, etc.), and proper configuration at the CU level was needed to handle the delays introduced in our GEO transparent scenario for Radio Resource Control (RRC) and F1 control-plane messages using the F1 application protocol (F1AP) interface. In the latter case, procedures such as *UE Context Setup* require an acknowledgment within a specific timeframe. If these timers are too short, the CU will conclude that the DU is non-responsive due to the delay and will drop the connection before the response arrives. Based on these experiments, we conclude that regenerative GEO scenarios, where RU and DU units are onboarded on the satellite, are viable. Once the configurations for unified CU and NTN DU were clearly defined, we enhanced our cloud-native artefacts for O-RAN CU and DU entities to handle unification and provide the *intended* NTN and TN configuration to the components during deployment, thus contributing to simplified and automated lifecycle management.

III. DEMONSTRATION

This demonstration showcases the deployment of a cloud-native, open-source, disaggregated 5G network that unifies TN and NTN segments under an O-RAN-compliant architecture. The involved mobile network functions (NFs) are packaged as separate NSs, allowing management through our MANO stack for unified orchestration and flexible, portable deployments. The main steps of the demonstration are as follows:

- 1) We request our MANO platform to deploy the artefacts corresponding to a single slice core network. As in [6], *slice-related* NFs (i.e., SMF and UPF) are decoupled from the control-plane NFs. Once deployed, the information for the NTN_UE and the TN_UE is included in the UDR database.
- 2) An OSC Near-RT RIC instance is deployed in clusterA [7]. We onboard a custom monitoring xApp in the OSC Near-RT RIC instance. Upon execution, this xApp will connect with the E2 manager component of the Near-RT RIC to obtain the list of available E2 nodes and to listen to the specified KPM metrics.

Fig. 2. Reported metrics by the NTN_DU and TN_DU when establishing a ping connection between UPF and TN_UE and NTN_UE

3) Then, we deploy the CU instance through our MANO platform. The CU component is configured with appropriate timeout settings at the RRC and F1AP connections to handle the two different DUs.

4) We proceed with deploying the TN_DU in Cluster B and the NTN_DU in Cluster C. Both DUs are configured to connect to the AMF in Cluster A, using 5 MHz bandwidth and 15 KHz subcarrier spacing. Additionally, the NTN_DU instance in Cluster C is configured to handle a GEO non-regenerative satellite scenario, including appropriate RRC timers.

5) Once both DU instances are active, the custom monitoring xApp is launched through the available remote xApp management Application Programming Interface (API) [7]. This xApp is launched to monitor the *DRB.UEThpDL*, *DRB.UEThpUL*, *DRB.AirIfDelayUL*, *DRB.RlcDelayUL*, *RRU.PrbUsedDL*, *RRU.PrbUsedUL* KPM metrics.

6) Next, we attach the TN_UE to the network, and it receives an IP address from the configured data network name (DNN), called *internet*.

7) Next, we start the NTN_UE component² which registers with the mobile network and receives an IP address in the range of the configured *internet* DNN.

8) Finally, we create an iperf3 traffic session between the NTN_UE and the TN_UE. The monitoring xApp traces show the metrics reported by the different E2 nodes, i.e., TN_DU and NTN_DU, as depicted in Fig. 2.

During the demonstration, the various steps are shown using the graphical user interface (GUI) of the MANO platform and different command line interface (CLI) windows displaying the registration logs at the Near-RT RIC subscription manager pod or the reported KPM metrics by the NTN_DU and TN_DU when establishing traffic sessions at the NTN_UE and TN_UE, as depicted in Fig. 2.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This demonstration has shown the feasibility and practicality of unifying TN and NTN segments under a fully softwareized O-

²The NTN_UE is started with a script that also starts the software channel emulator, considering a GEO satellite altitude of 36,000 km.

RAN-compliant architecture. By decoupling the NTN gNB into independent CU and DU components, we show that a single CU can manage both TN and NTN DUs. Our experimental setup shows that, despite the significant propagation delays inherent in GEO transparent scenarios, proper configuration of control-plane timers (e.g., F1AP and RRC procedures) enables stable and reliable connections for UEs in the different segments.

Using a Near-RT RIC instance and a custom monitoring xApp, we demonstrate real-time KPM collection from heterogeneous DUs, enabling unified observability for efficient optimization through closed-loop control. The MANO-driven deployment using Helm-packaged artefacts further confirms that cloud-native approaches greatly simplify lifecycle management, improving the reproducibility and portability of TN-NTN integrated systems. Overall, this work provides a concrete, practical step toward next-generation TN-NTN convergence. It also enables more advanced future-work scenarios, such as regenerative GEO or LEO constellations, where RU and DU functionalities may be partially or fully onboarded on satellites while still being orchestrated through the same O-RAN control and automation framework.

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